

A MDO TIBETAN HERDERS TRAVEL TO THAILAND, SINGAPORE, AND MALAYSIA FOR TWELVE DAYS (2016)

Rdo rje dpal 'byor རྡོ་རྗེ་དཔལ་པོ་ལྷོ་རྩེ། (Duoji huanjiao 多吉环角)*

ABSTRACT

Nineteen Tibetans from Bon skor (Wangshenke) Community, Bya mdo (Shagou) Township, Mang ra (Guinan) County, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture and four Chinese from Ping'an County, Haidong City, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China traveled to Thailand, Singapore, and Malaysia encountering new culinary experiences, customs, religious sites and activities, tourist resorts, and cultural differences.

KEYWORDS

A mdo Tibetan travel, Southeast Asian travel, Singapore, Thailand, Malaysia, Tibetan international travel

INTRODUCTION

In early January 2016, I was at home, having just left my university in Beijing, where I had drifted aimlessly for one semester. I had majored in Air Service, destined to be a flight attendant after graduation. Every day, I was required to learn how to make-up, dress well, and engage in various physical exercises to maintain an attractive figure. I also had etiquette courses. English sessions related to airplane broadcasting were provided, but students rarely focused. Most were from wealthy families and had no worries about money. They were simply immersed in a comfort zone with no particular purpose in life. In a big hall, a teacher lectured to hundreds of students sitting in steep rows. Only a few concentrated while others slept, chatted, or busied themselves with their cellphones. This was our boring, tedious, and meaningless routine. It was not what I wanted, so I dropped out of school with my family's approval.

After a few days at home, my father said, "Good news! We're going to travel to Thailand, Malaysia, and Singapore!"

One of Father's Chinese friends had told him about an opportunity to travel abroad. He then informed some local people, who agreed to go. While other travel destination options, such as Japan, Taiwan, and Hong Kong, were available, the decision was made to go to Thailand, Malaysia, and Singapore because we could visit three countries relatively inexpensively.

Hardly able to believe this, I was exhilarated! It was my first time traveling abroad.

Though Father had never attended a formal school, he had taught himself written Tibetan and is fluent in the Qinghai Chinese dialect. He has been, and in some cases, still is a herdsman, farmer, driver, businessman, and community leader. Father loves our family and often takes us to travel and on pilgrimage, but we had never been abroad.

Twenty-three people (sixteen men, seven women) were on the twelve-day journey, including my parents and me. We were all from Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. I was nineteen and the youngest. Except for four Chinese from Ping'an County, Haidong City, the rest of us were Tibetans from Bon skor (Wangshenke) Community, Bya mdo (Shagou) Township, Mang ra (Guinan) County, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture. The average tour member was about fifty years

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old, illiterate in Chinese (except for the Chinese), and a herder or farmer. It was a thrill for all of us to travel abroad.

Younger people are eager to travel, but their family's economic conditions restrict them, so any opportunity that arose usually went to their parents and grandparents.

A travel agency was in charge of all trip arrangements, including passports, visas, hotels, meals, and flight tickets. Each person was required to pay 6,200RMB.

We were instructed to pack summer and winter clothes, given the weather difference between Southeast Asian countries and Mtsho sngon. My parents also packed *rtsam pa* 'barley flour with butter and cheese', cooked mutton, and fried bread to be on the safe side.

STARTING OFF

Our expedition began one chilly morning when we left our community for Zi ling (Xining, the capital city of Mtsho sngon Province) as a group in several cars.

That afternoon, all the tour members assembled in the travel agency office. A staff member stepped out to welcome us when we reached the office threshold and offered us each a cup of water. Our Chinese companions had already arrived. Most of the Tibetan travelers wore Tibetan robes. A few minutes later, a young Chinese woman appeared with a document under her left arm, introduced herself as our tour guide, recited detailed regulations, and described the trip. She spoke only Mandarin, which was an issue for the Tibetan elders who understood no Chinese and had had almost no interaction with Chinese people.

Consequently, I was asked to translate to Tibetan, though most group members were not listening. The room brimmed with chatting. When we were required to fill out forms in Chinese, I assisted our Tibetan members.

A coach soon arrived. We loaded our luggage and set off for Caojiabao Airport, which we reached two hours before our flight took off. I helped the tour guide take all the flight tickets from the ticket-dispensing machine and check in our luggage. Earlier, she had given specific instructions on what was prohibited when checking in and what could not be in carry-on items. The only problem that emerged was overweight luggage for two travelers whose families had packed a lot of food - homemade bread, cooked meat, barley flour, and so forth - in case the elders would be unaccustomed to the food in foreign countries.

Next, everyone passed through the security check. The inspectors told us to remove our shoes and socks. Certain security personnel had a cold attitude and slowed our process, maybe because we were wearing Tibetan robes. A man aggressively ordered us to take our items swiftly from containers that passed through the scanners. All of the group got through except for Rgya mtsho, a middle-aged man.

"Open your bag!" ordered a young male inspector, who dug out a bottle of shampoo, a tube of hair oil, and a little knife and informed one of our members that they were prohibited items.

"Don't worry, the knife is for eating meat," boomed Rgya mtsho, who speaks loudly by nature and is gifted at making jokes. "Why can't I take them with me? I need them," said Rgya mtsho in Qinghai Chinese dialect, but he had to discard them.

We next headed toward the boarding gate, and I escorted some elders to the toilet. Later, as I sat with my mother in a waiting room, an elderly woman sitting beside me confided nervously, "I've never been on a plane. I'm a bit afraid."

"Don't worry, it will be fun," I comforted.

There were no vacant seats in the waiting room. All the men were standing and chatting and even laughing.

We soon started to line up at the boarding gate, and before long, the plane took off. One and a half hours later, we reached Xi'an at dusk. We gathered at the baggage claim zone, where our tour guide waved a flag. Everyone took their luggage to a coach that was waiting for us at the terminal gate. We boarded and went to a hotel where two people shared a double room. I shared a room with the tour guide.

Father proclaimed enthusiastically, "Shaanxi noodles are famous, so let's eat out!"

We then went to a Shaanxi noodle restaurant near the hotel and ate noodles (*youpomian*). Mother complained, "It's better to eat barley flour and bread. These noodles are so spicy they'll make me sick."

The next morning, we embarked on an early flight to Thailand. This time no one had trouble during the security check. I saw the elders enjoying the views outside the plane windows, including the woman worried about flying.

"Nowadays, everything is so convenient. People born in this century are so lucky! We are traveling from one country to another, Unbelievable!" said an old man fingering a string of prayer beads.

Throughout the flight, the time and distance we had flown were regularly announced. After five hours, a flight attendant informed us that the plane was descending in preparation for landing. I peered out the plane window and saw the landscape of verdant trees and lawns, as well as the sparkling golden temples of Bangkok. "Why are there such huge differences between this country and mine? We are geographically very near, so why are the climates so different?" I puzzled.

I had come from a place where it was winter and snowing, and everything was ashy, but here, in Bangkok, it was summer, and everywhere was green.

BANGKOK ARRIVAL

As we landed safe and sound, the flight attendant reported it was around forty degrees Celsius outside.

People from all over the world were at the airport. It seemed as though we had come to another planet. We were astonished to see Muslim women covered from head to toe in long black dresses and black veils. They were peering out from eye holes in complete veils. They were different from Muslim women in China, which does not have such strict clothing rules.

We changed RMB to Baht at the airport. One RMB was five Baht. Everybody was thrilled to use foreign money for the first time. The weather was hot and humid. I was sweating and found it hard to breathe.

Later, a Thai woman, in her thirties with long dark hair and big eyes with double eyelids, approached us and warmly announced, "Welcome to Thailand!" in Mandarin before leading us to a big blue tourist bus with a black driver.

I was astonished that the driver's seat was on the right instead of the bus' left side. When we boarded, the driver smiled at us. When some of our tour members said, "Hello!" the only English they knew, he smiled and nodded in greeting.

The air-conditioned bus was cool and comfortable. On the way to our hotel, our Thai tour guide taught us a Thai greeting, "*Sah wah dee kha*," to which we all repeated, "*Sah wah dee kha*" excitedly, including the men and women in their sixties.

We saw people wearing light clothes, shorts, T-shirts, skirts, and sandals. We had been told to wear thin clothes, but most of us wore long-sleeved shirts and pants, which were too hot in Bangkok. Tibetan elders are unaccustomed to wearing shorts in public.

We reached a hotel located in a big compound with a fountain, lawn, and trees and were immediately offered a buffet supper at the hotel restaurant. I thought there would be Thai food, but there were only Chinese dishes. After dinner, we all went shopping near the hotel. All writing was in Thai, which I thought resembled the Arabic on Muslim restaurant signs in China. We communicated with shopkeepers through gestures. We met our fellow Tibetans in a clothing shop where we bought T-shirts and shorts. The clothes were very colorful with various patterns, including elephants, the national symbol of Thailand. We wanted to talk with the local people, but language was a barrier.

Later that evening, everyone was asked to tip five Baht for the hotel attendant who would clean the room after we left the next day.

In the morning, as I was leaving the room, I met a young female hotel attendant in the corridor, who greeted, "*Sah wah dee kha*," while joining her palms in front of her chest and lowering her head.

I said, "*Sah wah dee kha*," shyly, without bowing.

On the third day, we visited the Royal Throne Hall Museum, with magnificent architecture. We were all fascinated by the Museum's stunning grounds with its green lawns and vibrant flowers, so we busily took selfies and group photos.

The building's interior and exterior designs were both splendid. The Thai monarchy's history was featured in paintings, images, and artistic work in gold and silver. Sculpted images and illustrations were on every wall and ceiling. Soldiers stood in every corner of the courtyard. Royal places in Thailand have a strict dress code requiring women to wear skirts instead of shorts when visiting.

Though particular designated places were luxurious, some parts of the city appeared old, run-down, and chaotic.

Transportation in Bangkok included buses, taxis, motorcycles, and tuk-tuk 'auto-rickshaws'. Most coaches in Thailand were double-deckers with colorful rainbow-like paintings and decorations.

Every several kilometers on the streets were Portraits of both the King and Queen of Thailand. "The King of Thailand is a good man because he has had only one wife. Most Thai men have more than one wife," our tour guide informed us.

There are thousands of Buddhist Temples in Thailand. Thai men are expected to join monastic life at least once in their life, to show gratitude to their parents. I was shocked that many men could be temporary monks, which differs from Tibetan Buddhist monks.

We dined at a buffet restaurant on the eightieth floor of the Baiyoke Tower, the tallest building in Bangkok, where we could view all of Bangkok. An older woman with acrophobia was scared of standing by the window while others enthusiastically took photos while enjoying the majestic views. Everyone was happy with the abundant food choices in that restaurant, including Chinese dishes, Japanese sushi, and various seafood. Tibetans in my home community don't eat seafood, but Rgyal mtsho held a plate with a big crab and said, "Let's spoil ourselves and not miss this golden chance."

Some elders looked at him disappointedly. Local Tibetans think that eating seafood is more sinful than eating mutton or yak meat.

A woman PRtained, "There was diced fruit near my seat a moment ago. I liked it, but it's not here now. Weird!"

Finally, we found it on the other side and realized that the seats were revolving.

"How ridiculous!" she said.

It was dark when we finished eating. The luminous cityscape, the orange glow of lamps, and vehicle lights made the streets sparkle. Streets were straight and winding, stretching in every direction among the tall buildings enveloped in smog in this crowded, noisy, modern metropolis.

On the fourth day, we visited the Grand Palace at Bangkok's heart, along with a multitude of other tourists. The distinctive design of the palace, temples, and stupas impressed with a dazzling golden brightness. We were required to remove our shoes before entering a temple housing a large

Buddha image. Many visitors knelt with their palms joined in worshipping the Buddha image. We did the same.

In the afternoon, we boarded a ship for a river cruise, along with a lot of Chinese tourists. Soon we were offered a meal. Spaghetti, pizza, and Chinese dishes were laid out on tables in the center of the ship, and people pushed and squeezed around them. Thai singers performed Chinese songs instead of Thai songs, perhaps because the majority of tourists were Chinese. Later, they chose singers from the audience, including a young fellow Tibetan who loves singing. He performed a Tibetan folk song. We enjoyed the beautiful scenery and sunset as the ship glided down the river.

When the river cruise ended, we boarded a bus to an auditorium to watch transgender performers dressed in gowns with adornments such as hairpins with white feathers and sparkling golden necklaces. They danced in line with different props, such as fans and pieces of cloth. They resembled female demons in the TV show *Journey to the West* who dance to seduce Monk Tangseng while he is searching for Buddhist scriptures to bring back to China.

In the end, a muscular woman came into the audience, pulled a man to the stage, and made him sit on a chair. Other women tied him up, wrapped a strip of cloth around his eyes, slapped his face, and otherwise toyed with him.

Later, when the woman came into the audience again, I was so scared that I jumped out of my seat and ran away in fear she would grab me. I had enjoyed the first part of the show. Still, the last part of the show terrified me, so when visitors took photos with the trans performers after the show outside the auditorium, I was afraid to approach and take pictures with them, even though I wanted to.

On the fifth day, we boarded a bus for Pattaya. Halfway there, we visited a park where visitors were entertained by interacting with tigers, monkeys, and pigs. A fun event was pigs running a race. Each pig was numbered, and when a man whistled, they began running.

A young man and woman in uniforms performed with the crocodiles. The woman tugged a crocodile's tail. Occasionally, it seemed irritated, opened its mouth, and bellowed. When it opened its mouth, the man put an upright stick between its palate and tongue for a while, removed it, and then put his head inside, which was frightening.

Later on, we went to a restaurant to eat roasted crocodile meat, soup, and dishes that the Chinese tourists eagerly enjoyed. Most Tibetans refused to eat the crocodile meat, although a few younger ones tried a little. When those who didn't ask, "How's the flavor?" Bsod nams rgyal replied, "It's tasty!"

A Chinese man assured them, "It's good for your health. You'll never find such good meat again!"

Eventually, a few more Tibetans were persuaded by the Chinese man to eat it. I also tried a bit. It was as white as bread and had a strong, fishy flavor.

When we emerged from the park, we were bewildered to see our framed photos on a desk. They had been taken as we had entered the park, but we hadn't noticed. A photographer with a camera on a strap around his neck explained that we could either pay and take the photos or not pay and leave them. Elders said, "It's not good to leave the photos there," so we paid and took all of our photos.

What a fun way to make money!

At dusk, we reached Pattaya, a prosperous coastal city famous for its beautiful beaches. We hung around Pattaya at night, boarding a medium-sized boat to a restaurant on the sea a few minutes from the seashore. We had supper there while transgender women wearing elaborate multicolored gowns danced on the stage in the restaurant's center. It was hard to guess that they were trans from their appearance. I curiously wondered why there were so many trans people in Thailand and why they wanted to change their gender.

Afterward, these performers came into the audience. A Chinese man embraced a trans woman and danced excitedly. Our table was near the stage where I was sitting with my mother, father, and some young Tibetan fellows. Two women came and urged the Tibetan men to dance with them. I was embarrassed and blushed, as such behavior is shameful among relatives. Hence, we left for another room and then returned to the seashore and strolled along a bustling pedestrian walkway. Bars and restaurants emitted vibrant, colorful lights. Loud, varied music exploded into the street. Many people were hanging around. Every doorway of every bar featured women wearing sexy clothes, waiting to welcome guests. It was very cheerful! As we walked along, we saw a man with a ghost mask standing on the road in front of us. He was very tall, had a white face with blood on his forehead, gray hair, and long black clothing. He stood on metal stilts that were about three meters tall. I was terrified and couldn't even gaze at him. However, others shook hands and posed for photos with him. It was all so different and exciting that we hung around until late in the night.

On the sixth day, we boarded a speedboat to a small island. In the middle of the sea, my fellow Tibetans and I tossed small colorful bags of grain we had prepared while at home for our family's wealth and prosperity. As we threw them into the sea, we all yelled, "*Lha rgyal lo!* Victory to the deities!"

As the boat sloshed back and forth, there was a lot of noise, and a woman shrieked, "Yul lha! Yul lha!" invoking the name of one of our local deities.

The island's impressive landscape resembled a picture featuring emerald woodland, a crystal-clear sea, and a cloudless blue sky. People on the beach were lying under umbrellas, while others were swimming and surfing. I suddenly imagined people having fun on a sea where piranhas attacked and ate them. This made me afraid to step into the sea as the waves lapped the beach. But eventually, I walked into the sea up to my waist. It was thrilling! I wanted to spend more time there, but our time was limited.

A little later, our tour guide led us to a concrete platform where people were parasailing. Elders were warned not to go there, but one older man insisted, "I don't want to miss this chance to parasail. I have no health issues."

Many parachutes in the sky were being towed behind a motorboat. Later, tour members who wanted to participate put on life jackets lined up, and one by one, excitedly flew up with their parachutes attached. After going around the platform three times, they landed, except for one of our group members, a middle-aged man, who fell into the sea after being airborne for only a few seconds. The boat pulling the parachute was far from him, though he was near the concrete platform where we stood. We could see his head in the distance. Luckily, two lifeguards quickly went out in another speedboat to rescue him. He smiled as he approached us and commented, "I thought I would see Gshin rje chos rgyal¹ today!"

On the seventh day, we headed to the Elephant Theater. How delightful elephants are! Many elephants strolled around the venue in an orderly line, following a mahout holding a sharp metal hook. Later, some adorable baby elephants came. A performance included the elephants standing in a line kicking a soccer ball into a net one by one. I was astonished by their human-like moves. Another impressive show was the mahout putting a paintbrush in an elephant's trunk that then painted flowers, which earned claps and shouts from the audience.

When the show ended, the elephants were allowed to move freely in the enclosure. Visitors gave them bananas. The elephants stuck out their trunks to take them and put them into their mouths. When we gave them money, they bowed their head and even knelt in thanks. Two elephants joined their trunks, making a seat for people and providing a perfect photo opportunity, which excited them.

¹ God of Death.

Earlier, I had read about elephant abuse online. Some were beaten to behave in certain ways. Some were slaughtered to make products from their ivory and skin. When I saw the metal hooks carried by the mahouts, I remembered that behind this impressive show was brutality - no wonder these majestic and powerful animals behaved so well, which depressed me. Many visitors were enjoying the show without knowing the suffering behind it.

Next, we mounted steps to a platform where you could sit in a carriage on the back of an elephant. "This is not good. Riding an elephant reduces your fortune. Elephants are revered animals," cautioned some Tibetan elders. Nevertheless, a few young Tibetan men ignored this and enjoyed sitting in the carriage.

That evening, when we were on the bus, our tour guide announced, "We will see a trans sex show!" in Chinese.

I was bewildered and shocked. I had no idea what kind of show it would be, but I thought it must be inappropriate to watch with relatives. There was no reaction from my fellow Tibetan travelers. Clearly, they did not understand. I explained to our Chinese tour guide the taboos among relatives, and she also thought it was improper. Finally, she arranged for all of us Tibetan women to visit an art gallery near the theater that featured creative drawings while the men and two Chinese women watched the show. Later, as we were waiting for our fellow tour members, the two Chinese women returned. One, who was very red in the face, announced with embarrassment, "It's crazy!"

The Tibetan women had no idea what she had said. After I explained, Glu mo, a middle-aged woman, said, "It must be a disgraceful show."

The others giggled.

SINGAPORE

On the eighth day, we flew to Singapore. As we exited the airport, a sudden storm caught us in a downpour, but we enjoyed it because the rain brought cooler weather.

Eventually, a new tour guide came with a bus to pick us up. On the bus, she briefly introduced Singapore: "The Garden City is another name for Singapore. It rains nearly every day during the monsoon, which is from November to January."

We just happened to be there during that time - January.

The rain stopped after a few minutes. As we looked through the bus windows, we beheld extremely clean and tidy surroundings. We saw no trash on the streets. Lawns and trees on both sides of the road were orderly, and after the rain, they were glossy and green. We visited a place near the sea that featured modern buildings of distinctive designs.

On the ninth day, we visited a duty-free shop that sold rings, earrings, bracelets, and necklaces with various gemstones. Most of my fellow travelers didn't like them because they were very small compared to Tibetan adornments featuring coral and turquoise that are much larger.

Singapore is a small country, so we only spent one day visiting tourist sites. There were undoubtedly other sites to see and explore. Singapore was an attractive, orderly country, and I hope to visit again.

MALAYSIA

In the afternoon of the ninth day, we proceeded to Malaysia by bus, which took four hours. On the way, we saw many cars going in both directions. Our tour guide explained that motorists commuted between Malaysia and Singapore for work or business though they were in two separate countries.

When we arrived, we were taken near a harbor to see the famous Straits of Malacca, between the Malay Peninsula and Indonesia, an important shipping channel for many countries. At the port, there were many multicolored shipping containers and cargo ships. I was excited to see the Straits of Malacca because I had learned about it in a high school geography class, though I recalled nothing except its name. I posted a video of the bustling harbor with my location - The Straits of Malacca - on WeChat and soon got many likes. My former classmates commented, "Wow! The Straits of Malacca!" "I'm looking forward to going there."

On the tenth day, as we took an elevator down in our hotel, someone unintentionally pressed the emergency button, which set off a constantly ringing alarm. The elevator stopped moving, dumbfounding us all. After a few seconds, the bell stopped ringing, and we heard a man's voice through a speaker in the elevator, asking, "Do you need help?"

"No, thanks! We just pressed the wrong button," I said, and the elevator soon resumed operation.

Everyone then asked, "What did you just say? If you were not here, we would be in trouble."

Feeling a little happy, I thought, "English is useful!"

Malaysia is well-known for its white coffee, so we visited some shops selling flavored coffee, chocolate, and cookies. The salesman offered us small cups of various coffee to taste. Some were bitter, and some were sweet. An old man sipped one cup PRTaiming, "This is terrible! It tastes burnt!"

Most of our group members bought a few packs of coffee and chocolate, even though they didn't like them very much, as gifts for family members and friends.

Our bus soon stopped in Kuala Lumpur so we could photograph the very modern, majestic Petronas Twin Towers, where Petronas, Malaysia's national petroleum company, is headquartered.

In the afternoon, we took a cable car to a mountaintop with an elevation of 1,800 meters, where there were many tall buildings, hotels, and entertainment venues. It was much cooler than in the lowland. Visitors filled the hotel lobby. I thought it would be hard to find a hotel room, but that hotel building had thousands of rooms, to my surprise. After our rooms were arranged, we were told of a big casino nearby. Most of the men were excited to hear this and went to observe people gambling. I also wanted to visit, but I didn't because the women disapproved, saying, "It's not an ideal place to go."

In my home community, gambling has been a bad influence. Some men gamble obsessively, bringing massive financial losses to their families.

On the eleventh day, at noon, we headed to the airport. Around six that afternoon, we flew back to China. Five hours later, we were back in Xi'an, where the weather was icy-cold. We again donned our warm Tibetan robes before being taken to a hotel for the night.

RETURNING HOME

The next day, everyone was eager to return home. After a quick breakfast at the hotel, we boarded a bus to the airport and took a ninety-minute flight to Xining. On the plane, our group leaned back in their seats. Some slept. Exhaustion from our journey lined their faces. When we reached the airport, our relatives were waiting, holding white *kha btags*¹ in welcome. "Let's go eat our local noodles and meat," some tour members said.

Throughout the journey, food was a problem for most of our Tibetan members. We, especially the elders, were used to mutton and yak meat, which were unavailable in the places we visited. There

¹ A white strip of cloth made of silk or wool.

must be great cuisines in those countries, but the travel agency arranged for us to eat at touristy restaurants that mainly provided food that was not memorable.

There are huge differences between my home area and the countries I visited. Thailand is a nation of friendly people and abundant natural resources, including marine environments. The utilization of local resources included training elephants and crocodiles to perform to attract visitors. In contrast, most people in my home area depend on herding and farming. Locals lack the economic means and know-how to use local resources effectively. Travel to modern, urbanized countries gives new ideas for a better future we want to help create.

My father enjoyed the journey. He appreciates unique architecture and designs and especially appreciated the Thai temples. He also thinks travel helps him relax and feel free from life's many stresses. However, my mother didn't enjoy the journey very much. She doesn't like noisy, crowded urban areas. Instead, she likes quiet places, and often goes to monasteries to chant, circumambulate, and prostrate.

A few days after the journey, when we looked through our photos, she said, "I don't see much difference between these countries and ours. They are both full of tall buildings and cars. I felt exhausted when I traveled around the city. I should go on pilgrimage and prostrate."

This discovery journey helped me realize the significance of studying other people's culture and life, which offers insight into the world and helps eliminate ignorance and misconceptions. I discovered how little I knew about the world and how useful English is in connecting with cultures and people beyond my local world.

PHOTOGRAPHS

FIG 1. Tibetan travelers at the Xi'an Xianyang International Airport in Shaanxi Province (January 2016, Rdo rje dpal 'byor).

FIG 2. Tibetan travelers at a cafeteria in Bangkok (2016, Rdo rje dpal 'byor).

FIG 3. The Grand Palace in Bangkok, Thailand (2016, Rdo rje dpal 'byor).

FIG 4. Yul lha thar on a White Orchid river cruise in Bangkok, Thailand (2016, Rdo rje dpal 'byor).

FIG 5. The Grand Palace (Bangkok, 2016, Rdo rje dpal 'byor).

FIG 6. Tibetan travelers on a speedboat in the Gulf of Thailand (2016, Rdo rje dpal 'byor).

FIG 7. Chinese tour guide, Luan Xiaozhu (left), Bsod nams rgyal (center), and Rdo rje dpal 'byor (right) (Pattaya, 2016, unknown photographer).

FIG 8. Btsun pa rgyal parasailing in Pattaya, Thailand (2016, Rdo rje dpal 'byor).

TIBETAN TERMS

a mdo ཨ་མདོ།

bon skor བོན་སྐོར།

bsod nams rgyal བསོད་ནམས་རྒྱལ།

bya mdo བྱ་མདོ།

btsun pa rgyal བཙུན་པ་རྒྱལ།

gshin rje chos rgyal གཤིན་རྗེ་ཚོས་རྒྱལ།

gter གཏེར།

kha btags ཁ་བཏགས།

klu mo ལུ་མོ།

lha rgyal lo ལྷ་རྒྱལ་ལོ།

mang ra མང་ར།

mtsho lho མཚོ་ལྷོ།

mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྔོན།

rdo rje dpal 'byor རྡོ་རྗེ་དཔལ་འབྱེར།

rgya mtsho རྒྱ་མཚོ།

rtsam pa རུམ་པ།

yul lha ཡུལ་ལྷ།

yul lha thar ཡུལ་ལྷ་ཐར།

zi ling ཟི་ལིང།

CHINESE TERMS

Caojiabao 曹家堡

Duojiahuanjiao 多吉环角

Guinan 贵南

Hainan 海南

Haidong 海东

Luan Xiaozhu 栾小竹

Ping'an 平安

Qinghai 青海

Shagou 沙沟

Shaanxi 陕西

Tangseng 唐僧

Wangshenke 汪什科

Xi'an 西安

Xianyang 咸阳

Xining 西宁

youpomian 油泼面